

A Shift-Share Analysis of the Manufacturing Employment at uMhlathuze Local Municipality.

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ABSTRACT

This paper uses Shift-Share Analysis (SSA) to measure the performance of uMhlathuze manufacturing industry in terms of employment in light of the government emphasis on stimulating the growth of manufacturing sector in an attempt to create jobs. The paper set out two objectives, firstly, to establish if uMhlathuze manufacturing employment is growing or declining, and secondly, to identify uMhlathuze manufacturing divisions that are specialising in employment. The study sampled manufacturing employment data from 2010 to 2017 and performed an analysis using SSA components, those are, the industrial mix effect (IME), regional competitive effect (RCE) and allocation effect (AE). The results showed that the municipality performed poorly in terms of employment since it recorded negative IME and AE. This suggested that uMhlathuze manufacturing experiences slow employment growth when compared to other economic sectors. The results also suggested that during the period of analysis, uMhlathuze municipality did not rely on the manufacturing sector for employment. With these results, we learn that the emphasis of government strategy on job creation through manufacturing growth is not justified since the manufacturing sector is shrinking in employment. Therefore, we recommended a clear strategy that focuses on protection of labour-intensive manufacturing firms and its supply chain.

Keywords: Allocation Effect, Esteban-Marquillas Model, Manufacturing Employment, Industrial Mix Effect, Shift-Share Analysis

1. Introduction

The National Development Plan (NDP) (2014) and the KwaZulu-Natal Provincial Growth and Development Plan (KZN PGDP) (2016) emphasise the importance of stimulating manufacturing productivity with an aim of creating jobs for locals. Furthermore, the NDP and KZN PGDP also recognises the manufacturing sector as an important role player in delivering significant job creation (NDP, 2014; KZN PGDP, 2016). Conversely, global and domestic trends suggest a continuous decline in manufacturing employment (Rodrik, 2016; Buckley and Majumdar, 2018). Also, the scholarship has shown evidence of considerable decline in labour intensity within the South African manufacturing sector. For example: in 1970, every R1 million invested in manufacturing sector meant that 12 people were employed, however, an investment of R1 million employs 1 person at present (Black, Craig, Dunne, 2017). The significant decline of labour intensity challenges the emphasised necessity to focus on stimulating the growth of manufacturing sector with a hope to create jobs. While the backbone of this paper is founded on the disconnect between government strategies on manufacturing sector and the actual performance of manufacturing employment, there is a belief that an industry growth/decline in

one area may not be evident in another area since economic performances vary from region to region. (Leigh and Blakely, 2016). It is for this reason that this paper became relevant as it interrogate the performance of uMhlathuze Local municipality manufacturing employment. This paper has two objectives: firstly, to identify the manufacturing divisions that are growing/declining in terms of employment, and secondly, to identify uMhlathuze manufacturing divisions that are specialising in employment. To achieve these objectives, this paper uses Shift-Share Analysis (SSA) to measure uMhlathuze manufacturing performance in terms of Industrial Mix Effect and Allocation Effect.

Traditionally, SSA is used as a technique to calculate and describe the patterns of the local economy, however, SSA could also be used to analyse the following with regards to a local manufacturing area: how competitive it is; the level of industrial or sectoral growth; how an area performs with regards to employment and its economy (Wilson, Su Chem, Ping and Robinson, 2005; Goschin, 2014; Dogru and Sirakaya, 2017). Predominantly, the SSA involves three effects, those are, national growth effect, industrial mix effect, and competitive share effect (Grossi and Mussini, 2018). The national growth effect aims to show the influence of the national economy on the local economy (Leigh and Blakely, 2016). It is understood that regardless of what industry it is, the national industry growth or decline impacts on the local area whether the impact is positive or negative. Therefore, the local area may benefit or suffer from the changes in the national industry performance (Leigh and Blakely, 2016). On the other hand, the industrial mix effect is the change attributable to differences in the industry make-up of the local area versus that of the nation (Mayor, Lopez, and Perez, 2007). Furthermore, the competitive share effect is what most regional planners base their focus on when they use shift-share analysis (Goschin, 2014; Leigh and Blakely, 2016). The competitive share effect shows the portion of the growth in a region that is attributable to the strengths or weakness of local firms relative to the firms within the same industry elsewhere (nation or province) (Oyewole, 2016).

Since its formalisation, SSA has been subjected to a variety of modifications in an attempt to strengthen the technique's relevance to various studies and also to address criticism. For example, Wilson *et al.* (2005) criticised SSA for its inability take economic changes into account as its primary focus is on the beginning and most recent year. In response to this, it is indicated that separating the period of analysis into more than one period and comparing them against on another would enable scholars to draw more accurate trends (Kleynhans and Sekhobela, 2011). Dogru and Sirakaya (2017) argued that even though the SSA is an analytic tool, it is unable to illustrate whether there are considerable changes in the decline or growth of the industry performance. Thus, others have proposal to incorporate SSA with regression analysis in an attempt to address the above mentioned SSA limitation (Patterson 1991; Dogru and Sirakaya, 2017).

Besides the identified limitations and modifications, SSA remains one of the widely used tools in the regional economic development and, is popular amongst regional planners and communities (Le Gallo and Kamarianakis, 2011; Grossi and Mussini, 2018). For instance, in the US, ESRI has incorporated a SSA calculator in their mapping website application and it can be used by the communities and regional planners at no charge (ESRI, 2018). Also, scholars such as Kleynhans and Claassen (2012) used SSA as a predictive technique when investigating the potential of manufacturing subindustries. Oyewole (2016) used SSA to analyse the competitiveness of regional services in the international market, and Grossi and Mussini (2018) have used SSA in analysing the changes in electricity consumption. The wide use of SSA is a result of its simplicity underpinned by the use of uncomplicated data that could be easily understood not only by economists, but also the general public without a theoretical and statistical expertise (Kleynhans and Sekhobela, 2011; Dogru and Sirakaya, 2017). In addition, SSA has understood to reduce the necessity to collect primary data (for example, surveys or interviews), which is considered to be an expensive and time-consuming process, instead, using this SSA saves costs and time (Dogru and Sirakaya, 2017). Based on the aforementioned advantages, the SSA was appropriate for the purposes of this paper.

The structure of this paper is as follows: the above section is an introduction in nature, and it unpacks the background of the South African manufacturing employment, the purpose this paper and the concept of SSA. The following section will discuss the methods/model in detail, specifically, the selection of the study area, data sampling and collection instruments, and the chosen model. The paper proceeds to discuss the results and findings in terms of Industrial Mix Effect and Allocation Effect. The last section concludes the paper and provides recommendations.

2. Methods

2.1 The Selection of the Study Area

McMillan and Schumacher (2001) stressed the importance of choosing a research site that would be suitable and accessible. The present study was conducted at the uMhlathuze Local Municipality in the KwaZulu-Natal (KZN) province on the basis of the municipality's manufacturing performance and potential. UMhlathuze manufacturing sector is the largest economic sector at uMhlathuze Local Municipality, contributing 30.5% in the GDP of the study area (uMhlathuze, 2017). The 30.5% contribution of the manufacturing sector is said to be partly attributed to the presence of firms such as South32, Tongaat Hullet, Bell Equipment and Mondi. Furthermore, the uMhlathuze Local Municipality inhabits one of seven areas identified as special economic zones in South Africa, that is, the Richards Bay Industrial Development Zone (RBIDZ) (Vallie, 2017). In addition, the Trade and Investment of KwaZulu-Natal (TIKZN) (2014) reported a total of 42 investment opportunities in KZN, and 19 of those opportunities were focused on manufacturing sector. Furthermore, the 9 of the 19 investment opportunities were found in the manufacturing sector of uMhlathuze Local Municipality (TIKZN,

2014). It is also noted that the RBIDZ has received manufacturing oriented investments estimated to be just above R7 billion which was equivalent to \$512million in 2016 (RBIDZ, 2016). These investments include a R4,5 billion (\$330m) of titanium plant, R1,5 billion (\$110m) Technopark, R500m (\$36m) for chemical plant; another R500m (\$36m) plant for the manufacture of energy storage with micro grid system; and R200m (\$13M) cement manufacturing factory (RBIDZ, 2016). These reports (RBIDZ and TIKZN) reflect a manufacturing sector potential at uMhlathuze Local Municipality. Based on the above evidence, the manufacturing sector plays and will play a significant role in the near future of uMhlathuze economy. Whilst not disputing the role and the contribution of manufacturing sector at uMhlathuze, the study understood that global and domestic trends of manufacturing employment remain in a downward trajectory and if uMhlathuze manufacturing employment faces a similar trajectory, the manufacturing sector contribution would be less meaningful to locals since sufficient jobs are not created and instead, there is an employment rate decline within the sector (Rodrik, 2016; Black *et al.* 2017). Therefore, the study was convinced that an investigation with regards to uMhlathuze manufacturing sector using SSA components is justified.

2.2 Data Collection Instrument, Sample and Sampling Technique

The study used a desktop data collection to retrieve uMhlathuze manufacturing employment data from Quantec Economic Trends Database (QETD). The University of Zululand subscribes to Quantec Databases and this enabled the researcher to use his university credentials to access the QETD. In this study, one of the advantages of using desktop data collection instrument is that the data is already stored and can be remotely retrieved from databases (Dogru and Sirakaya-Turk, 2017). In terms of sample size, the study sampled ten manufacturing divisions that make up uMhlathuze manufacturing sector from the Quantec Economic Trends Database (QETD). These manufacturing divisions are food, beverages and tobacco; secondly, textiles, clothing, leather and footwear; thirdly, wood, wood products, paper, publishing and printing; fourth, other non-metal mineral products; fifth, coke, petroleum, chemical products, rubber and plastic; sixth, metals, metal products, machinery and equipment; seventh, electrical machinery and apparatus; eighth, transport equipment; ninth, radio, TV, instruments, watches and clocks; and, finally, furniture, other manufacturing and recycling.

The study employed a time-series sampling in which the manufacturing data (which is industry employment) is from 2010 – 2017. Time-series is used to sample large data with a purpose to discover reliable trends and logical relationship between variables of interest (Uma Devi, Sundar and Alli, 2013). The study was convinced that this period (2010-2017) was adequate to understand the employment trends of the uMhlathuze manufacturing sector. Similar to SSA studies, the literature shows that desktop data collection and time-series sampling are widely used within the field. Evidently, scholarship (Mayor *et al.* 2007; Goschin, 2014; Oyewole, 2016; Dogru and Sirakaya-Turk, 2017; Grossi and Mussini, 2018) has used numerous databases to obtain quantitative data and have also used time-series sampling when using SSA.

2.3 Shift-Share Analysis: The Esteban-Marquillas Model

The SSA of Esteban-Marquillas model (ES model) is partially informed by Dunn's (1960) traditional model (Dunn, 1960; Esteban-Marquillas, 1972). Furthermore, both the traditional model and Esteban-Marquillas model are able consider economic changes during the period of analysis (Dunn, 1960; Esteban-Marquillas, 1972; Fuchs *et al.* 2000). In the Esteban-Marquillas model, the industry average growth rates play a central role in factoring in economic changes (could be employment growth/decline). For instance, if the period of analysis was year 2000 – 2010, the model would establish an industry average employment growth rate (factoring in year on year industry performance) and subsequently using it where applicable when calculating the IME, RCSE and AE. Aside from the above, the contribution of Esteban-Marquillas in SSA is primarily focused on distinguishing the industrial mix from the regional competitive share effect. This is because Esteban-Marquillas was convinced that the regional competitive share effect is unable to calculate what it pretends to calculate since it is influenced and linked to industrial mix effect (Esteban-Marquillas, 1972). The understanding was that this link between the industrial mix and competitive share effect presents a major limitation in the traditional model since the SSA aims to show if the performance of an regional industry is unique to that of a province/nation (Esteban-Marquillas, 1972). In addressing the limitation of the traditional, the Esteban-Marquillas rearranged the traditional model by decomposing regional competitive share effect into two components, those were, a new regional competitive share effect that is not correlated with industrial mix and introduces an allocation effect (Esteban-Marquillas, 1972). The introduction of allocation effect makes the ES model to have four effects, those are, National Growth Effect (NGE), Industrial Mix Effect (IME); Regional Competitive Share Effect (RCSE) and Allocation Effect (AE). Therefore, the Esteban-Marquillas model follows this expression:

$$E_{ir} = NG_i + IM_i + RCS_i + AL_i \quad (1)$$

Let E_{ir} = employment growth in an industry of a region; NG_i = national growth effect; IM_i = industrial mix effect, RCS_i = regional competitive share effect and AL_i = allocative effect.

Notwithstanding the above expression (1), this paper focused on the two effects (those are, Industrial Mix Effect and Allocation Effect) with Regional Competitive Share Effect as an additional effect. The nature of the objectives of this paper warranted the withdrawal of national growth effect (NGE) in favour of the Industrial Mix Effect (IME); Regional Competitive Share Effect (RCSE) and Allocation Effect (AE). Therefore; the model of this paper follows this expression:

$$E_{ir} = IM_i + CS_i + AL_i \quad (2)$$

Where:

$$IM_i = b_{ir} (e_{i0} - e_{00}) \quad (3)$$

$$CS_i = H_{ir} (E_{ir} - B_{i0}) \quad (4)$$

$$AL_i = (b_{ir} - H_{ir}) (E_{ir} - B_{i0}) \quad (5)$$

$$H_{ir} = Y_i \left(\frac{y_i}{Y}\right) \quad (6)$$

Let b_{ir} = employment in an industry of a region; e_{00} = average employment growth; e_{i0} = average employment growth rate of an industry; B_{i0} = provincial average employment growth rate of an industry; H_{ir} = homothetic industry employment in the region; Y_i = provincial employment in the industry; Y = total provincial employment, and y_i = total employment in a region.

In the above expression (2), the industrial mix component continues to play the same role to that it played in the traditional model (Dunn, 1960; Esteban-Marquillas, 1972). Traditionally, the IME is meant to show how fast or slow the manufacturing divisions would grow if uMhlathuze manufacturing income and employment average growth rates were equal to the provincial income and employment average growth rates (Leigh & Blakely, 2016; Grossi and Mussini, 2018). The study denounced the traditional IME as a result of the conviction that had it followed the above-mentioned IME, it would not provide the actual IME of the region since it is based on the hypothetical premise that “how local manufacturing sector would grow if its structure was equal to the employment”. Therefore, calculating IME using regional average growth rates would provide a more accurate understanding of how uMhlathuze manufacturing sector is performing when compared against the economy it operates within. Furthermore, the expectation is that IME will be greater than zero ($0 >$) if a specific manufacturing division of interest is growing than the local total employment growth rate of uMhlathuze economy. However, if the local manufacturing division is declining when compared against the employment growth rate of uMhlathuze economy, the IME is expected to be lesser than zero (< 0). Additionally, the Esteban-Marquillas model introduced a homothetic variable (6) which mainly represents the employment that an industry of a region would have if the employment of a region is the same as that of the province (Fuchs *et al.* 2000). The homothetic variable is a theoretical value in the industry that assumes that the industrial mix of a province is equal to that of a region (Fuchs *et al.* 2000).

The regional competitive share effect of the Esteban-Marquillas model give rise to another effect called the allocation effect to separate the assumed correlation between regional share component and the regional industrial mix found in the traditional model (Esteban-Marquillas, 1972; Fuchs *et al.* 2000). In this regard, the regional competitive share effect (4) indicates if a local manufacturing division has competitive advantages, whereas, the allocation effect (5) shows whether a local manufacturing division specialises in terms of employment. This could also be interpreted as an indicator that shows if a

manufacturing division holds a significant value in a local economy (Fuchs *et al.* 2000). Furthermore, the allocation effect will be greater than zero ($0 >$) if a region is specialised in that industry, and if a region is not specialised in that industry, the allocation effect will be less than zero (< 0) (Esteban-Marquillas, 1972; Fuchs *et al.* 2000). Through the industrial mix effect, regional competitive share effect and the allocative effect, the study would be able to find out manufacturing divisions whose employment declining faster and also identify manufacturing division that uMhlathuze manufacturing sector specialises in. This enables the study to detect manufacturing divisions whose contribution at uMhlathuze manufacturing employment is negative and also identify manufacturing divisions that enjoy competitive advantages offered by the uMhlathuze manufacturing environment.

3. Results and Discussion

3.1 Changes in Manufacturing Employment of uMhlathuze Local Municipality and KwaZulu- Natal

The general picture illustrated by raw data indicates that both manufacturing employment of uMhlathuze Local Municipality and KwaZulu-Natal province has declined during the period from 2010 to 2017. This is because uMhlathuze manufacturing employment of Local Municipality declined from 14 012 in 2010 to 13 199. During the same period (2010 – 2017), KwaZulu-Natal manufacturing employment declined from 294 436 in 2010 to 285 444 in 2017. In addition, Petroleum products, chemicals, rubber and plastic manufacturing showed the most positive growth with a job increase of 246 at uMhlathuze manufacturing sector and the food, beverages and tobacco manufacturing had the largest job growth (+4231) within the KwaZulu-Natal manufacturing sector.

Figure 1a: Manufacturing Employment of uMhlathuze Municipality

Source: Quantec Database, 2018 (Figures from raw data).

Figure 1a demonstrates that almost every manufacturing division recorded a positive growth except for wood, wood products, paper, publishing and printing; and metals, metal products, machinery and

equipment. Furthermore, the Metals, metal products, machinery and equipment manufacturing recorded the worst job loss (-1594) than any other manufacturing division at uMhlatuze Local Municipality. Conversely, the petroleum products, chemicals, rubber and plastic manufacturing division recorded the largest job growth of 246. Overall, the local manufacturing performance showed that in manufacturing divisions where there is growth, it is not significant as in instances where there is decline.

Figure 1b: Employment Statistics of KwaZulu-Natal

Source: *Quantec Database, 2018 (Figures derived from raw data).*

The figure above shows that the total manufacturing employment of KwaZulu-Natal has declined by 8992 during the period of analysis and three of the four divisions that recorded a decline had a job loss that is greater than 2000 each. Furthermore, the textile division recorded the largest job loss of 9406 where it lost 1344 annually between 2010 and 2017. Conversely, the food and beverages division had the largest job growth which was 4231 and it was growing by 604 annually between 2010 and 2017. In addition, as shown in the above graph that the majority of division grew in employment, however, divisions who decline in employment underwent severe job loss. For example, the job growth of division who grew in employment, grew by 10 965 and the divisions who decline in employment had a job loss of 19 957, therefore, totalling a provincial job loss of 8992.

3.2 A Shift-Share Analysis of uMhlatuze Manufacturing Sector

The following presentation of results and discussion is categorised in terms of the SSA components, namely, Industrial Mix Effect, Regional Competitive Share Effect and Allocation Effect.

3.2.1 Industrial Mix Effect (IME)

The IME is calculated by subtracting the uMhlatuze average employment growth rate from the uMhlatuze average employment growth in an industry, multiplied by the employment of the most recent year of uMhlatuze manufacturing division. The IME (IM_i) is calculated using the following expression:

$$IM_i = B_{ir} \left(\left(\frac{e_{i0}}{100} \right) - \left(\frac{e_{00}}{100} \right) \right) \quad (7)$$

B_{ir} = most recent year employment in an industry of a region; e_{i0} = uMhlathuze employment average growth rate of an industry; e_{00} = uMhlathuze employment average growth rate.

Table 1: shows the employment IME of uMhlathuze manufacturing sector

uMhlathuze Manufacturing Divisions	uMhlathuze 2017 Employment	Average Growth Rate		IME
		e_{i0}	e_{00}	
Food, beverages and tobacco (FBT)	2219	1.27%		-11
Textiles, clothing and leather goods (TCLG)	868	0.77%		-8
Wood and paper; publishing and printing (WPPP)	1666	-0.17%		-32
Petroleum products, chemicals, rubber and plastic (PPCRP)	1554	2.55%		13
Other non-metal mineral products (ONMMP)	710	2.49%		5
Metals, metal products, machinery and equipment (MMPME)	4258	-4.39%	1.75%	-261
Electrical machinery and apparatus (EMP)	214	2.02%		1
Radio, TV, instruments, watches and clocks (RTIWC)	117	1.46%		-2
Transport equipment (TE)	985	2.71%		9
Furniture; other manufacturing (FOR)	608	0.66%		-7
Total	13 199			-293

Source: Quantec Database, 2018 (Figures derived from raw data). Figures are rounded off to the nearest whole number (except growth rate and average growth rates).

Table 1 above reads that uMhlathuze manufacturing employment is growing slower than that of the overall employment of uMhlathuze municipality since it recorded a negative employment IME of -293. Furthermore, six of the ten divisions recorded a negative employment IME (those were, FBT; TCLG; WPPP; MMPME; RTIWC; FOR). Four divisions recorded a positive employment IME (PPCRP; ONMMP; EMP; TE). In addition, MMPME recorded the largest negative employment IME (-261) and was followed by the WPPP (-32), whereas, PPCRP recorded the largest employment IME of +13 AND was followed by the TE which recorded +9 employment IME.

The above results illustrate that uMhlathuze manufacturing sector is growing slower in terms of employment. The negative IME also suggests that uMhlathuze economy relied on other industries (this

could be agriculture, finance, mining or tourism) and not manufacturing sector for employment growth during the period of analysis.

3.2.2 Regional Competitive Share Effect

In the Esteban-Marquillas model, the RCSE is calculated by subtracting the provincial average employment/income growth rate of an industry from the employment/income growth rate in an industry of a region multiplied by the homothetic employment/income. The RCSE (CS_i) for the employment of uMhlathuze manufacturing sector is expressed by;

$$CS_i = H_{ir} (e_{ir} - B_{i0}) \quad (8)$$

H_{ir} = homothetic industry employment in the region [which is calculated by: $Y_i (\frac{y_i}{Y})$]; Y_i = provincial employment in the industry; Y = total provincial employment, and y_i = total employment in a region. e_{ir} = industry employment growth rate in the region; B_{i0} = provincial average employment growth rate of an industry.

Table 2 depicts RCSE employment of uMhlathuze manufacturing sector

uMhlathuze Manufacturing Divisions	Homothetic Employment H_{ir}	Growth Rate	Average Growth Rates	RCSE
		e_{ir}	B_{i0}	
Food, beverages and tobacco (FBT)	2447	1.22%	1.13%	221
Textiles, clothing and leather goods (TCLG)	1490	0.71%	-3.20%	5825
Wood and paper; publishing and printing (WPPP)	1769	-0.23%	0.41%	-1129
Petroleum products, chemicals, rubber and plastic (PPCRP)	1615	2.49%	1.12%	2217
Other non-metal mineral products (ONMMP)	349	2.46%	-0.25%	947
Metals, metal products, machinery and equipment (MMPME)	2030	-4.45%	-2.01%	-4945
Electrical machinery and apparatus (EMP)	239	1.79%	0.32%	352
Radio, TV, instruments, watches and clocks (RTIWC)	118	1.42%	0.92%	60
Transport equipment (TE)	1024	2.69%	1.54%	1183
Furniture; other manufacturing (FOR)	725	0.63%	-2.01%	1914
Total	11 808			6644

Source: Quantec Database, 2018 (Figures derived from raw data). Figures are rounded off to the nearest whole number (except growth rate and average growth rates).

Table 2 illustrates that uMhlathuze has a total homothetic employment of 11 808 which reflects the employment that uMhlathuze manufacturing sector would have if its employment structure was equal to that of KwaZulu-Natal province. UMhlathuze manufacturing sector recorded a total of +6644 in terms of RCSE employment. This positive RCSE indicates that uMhlathuze manufacturing sector possesses competitive advantages since eight local manufacturing divisions growth rate is higher than that of the provincial average growth rate of manufacturing divisions. TCLG division was found to have the largest competitive advantages in terms of employment (+5825) within manufacturing sector primarily because the manufacturing division had the poorest average growth rate in the KwaZulu-Natal province (-3.20%). In contrast, the MMPME division had the largest negative RCSE despite having a second largest homothetic employment. The poor RCSE in the MMPME division on the local manufacturing sector is caused by the poor growth rate (-4.45%) at uMhlathuze Local Municipality.

The above discussion has presented the results of the study of the RCSE on manufacturing employment of the uMhlathuze Municipality, the discussion proceeds to present the study findings of uMhlathuze Allocation Effect (AE) in terms of income and employment.

3.2.3 Allocation Effect (AE)

The AE is calculated by subtracting homothetic employment from the regional employment of an industry multiplied by results of subtracting the provincial average employment growth rate of an industry from the industry employment growth rate in the region. The calculation of employment AE (AL_i) follows this expression:

$$AL_i = (B_{ir} - H_{ir}) (e_{ir} - B_{i0}) \quad (6)$$

B_{ir} = employment in an industry of a region; H_{ir} = homothetic industry employment in the region; e_{ir} = industry employment growth rate in the region; B_{i0} = provincial average employment growth rate of an industry.

Table 3 shows the AE employment of uMhlathuze manufacturing sector

uMhlathuze Manufacturing Divisions	uMhlathuze 2017 employment	uMhlathuze Homothetic Employment H_{ir}	Growth Rates	Average Growth Rates	AE
			e_{ir}	B_{i0}	
Food, beverages and tobacco (FBT)	2219	2447	1.22%	1.13%	-21
Textiles, clothing and leather goods (TCLG)	868	1490	0.71%	-3.20%	-2433
Wood and paper; publishing and printing (WPPP)	1666	1769	-0.23%	0.41%	66
Petroleum products, chemicals, rubber and plastic (PPCRP)	1554	1615	2.49%	1.12%	-84
Other non-metal mineral products (ONMMP)	710	349	2.46%	-0.25%	979
Metals, metal products, machinery and equipment (MMPME)	4258	2030	-4.45%	-2.01%	-5427
Electrical machinery and apparatus (EMP)	214	239	1.79%	0.32%	-37
Radio, TV, instruments, watches and clocks (RTIWC)	117	118	1.42%	0.92%	0
Transport equipment (TE)	985	1024	2.69%	1.54%	-45
Furniture; other manufacturing (FOR)	608	725	0.63%	-2.01%	-310
Total	13 199	11 808			-7314

Source: Quantec Database, 2018 (Figures derived from raw data). Figures are rounded off to the nearest whole number (except growth rate and average growth rates).

Table 3 above shows that uMhlathuze manufacturing sector recorded a negative employment AE (-7314) where the MMPME division had the largest negative employment AE (-5427) and the ONMMP division had the largest positive employment AE (+979). On the basis of the -7314 employment AE, uMhlathuze Local Municipality does not specialise in terms of manufacturing employment. Specifically, uMhlathuze Local Municipality was found not to specialise in eight manufacturing divisions, those were, FBT, TCLG, PPCRP, MMPME, EMP, RTIWC, TE and FOR. The negative employment AE of seven manufacturing divisions (FBT, TCLG, PPCRP, EMP, RTIWC, TE and FOR) was caused by a homothetic employment that is larger than most recent year employment which negated the advantage of having a regional industry growth rate that is larger than the provincial industry average growth rate. In contrast to the above, the MMPME division recorded a negative AE as a result of a negative regional industry growth rate (-4.45%) and despite having a considerably larger most recent year employment than the homothetic employment. A positive employment AE was recorded by two manufacturing divisions, which are, WPPP division (+66) and ONMMP division (+979), meaning that uMhlathuze Local Municipality specialises in these divisions. While ONMMP division had a

considerably larger most recent year employment (710) and a larger regional industry growth rate (2.46%), surprisingly the WPPP division recorded a positive employment AE despite having most recent year employment that was smaller than homothetic employment and the regional industry growth rate that was also smaller than the provincial industry average growth rate.

3.3 Discussion of results

The IME results found that the employment of divisions such as FBT; TCLG; WPPP; MMPME; RTIWC; and FOR were found to be declining faster than the total employment average growth rate of uMhlathuze municipality. Furthermore, the IME results are supported by the raw data which suggest a decline in manufacturing employment for both uMhlathuze Municipality and KwaZulu-Natal province. In terms of AE and RCSE, the study found that the overall employment AE was negative with only two exceptions (that is, Wood and paper; publishing and printing; and Other non-metal mineral products) that recorded a positive AE, meaning that uMhlathuze manufacturing sector holds less contribution towards uMhlathuze employment. Against the slow growth and lack of specialisation in terms manufacturing employment, uMhlathuze manufacturing sector enjoys a considerable positive RCSE in terms of employment with an exception of two manufacturing divisions (those are, Wood and paper; publishing and printing and Metals, metal products, machinery and equipment) that recorded a negative RCSE. This is surprising because a positive RCSE suggests that uMhlathuze manufacturing employment possesses competitive advantages, yet the manufacturing employment records a very slow growth and the also the local municipality does not specialise in this economic sector.

4. Conclusion

The study learnt that the strategies that steer the direction of the country's economic development emphasised the stimulation of manufacturing sector in an attempt to create jobs (NDP, 2014; KZN PGDP, 2016). This occurred concurrently with the backdrop that the global and domestic manufacturing jobs are declining significantly. Therefore, the paper focused on finding out whether uMhlathuze manufacturing employment is following the decline trajectory shown by global and domestic manufacturing employment trends. Specifically, the study used SSA to understand the performance of manufacturing employment wherein the combined results showed that uMhlathuze manufacturing employment is declining and it does not rely on manufacturing sector for job creation. The SSA findings provided a clear picture that uMhlathuze manufacturing employment is unable to resist the global and domestic manufacturing employment trends. Therefore, the study concluded that the emphasis to further the development of manufacturing sector in an attempt to create jobs is not justified by the present manufacturing employment performance. Aside from the above, the study recommended a clear identification of labour-intensive divisions. It is unclear which manufacturing divisions are capital intensive and labour intensive and this blurs the potential to attract focus and investment on manufacturing divisions that would help create jobs. Therefore, identifying capital and intensive

manufacturing divisions would offer an opportunity to choose investments in manufacturing divisions that would be aligned to the mission or objectives of stimulating job creation.

The SSA Esteban-Marquillas model is limited to providing descriptive findings and cannot explain the underlying factors that are characterising the decline of manufacturing employment. Therefore, this limitation opens an area for further research that scholars can explore by conducting a study that would seek to identify and explain the internal/external factors and microeconomic/macroeconomic factors that influenced the downward trajectory of manufacturing employment.

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